

CBA_DREAMM: a diet and time-resolved multi-omics CBA gut microbiome resource

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Abstract:

The CBA mouse is an important model for studying gut microbial interactions; however, a microbiome infrastructure for this model did not exist. We announce a fecal CBA-specific microbiome resource that spans diet, time, and pathogen gradients. This resource includes amplicon, metagenomic, and metatranscriptomic sequencing, and metabolomics, to unveil microbial functionalities.

SECTION 1

The CBA mouse model is commonly used for immunology and enteric pathogen research, particularly for evaluating the impacts of *Salmonella enterica* serovar Typhimurium (*Salmonella*) during inflammation (1, 2). Notably, these mice display disease progression analogous to the disease manifestation in humans with localized gut infection rather than systemic spread. Specifically, CBA mice tolerate a high *Salmonella* load without antibiotic pretreatment, allowing a longer temporal infection study period and study of commensal microbes (3–5).

Additionally, diet plays a crucial role in chemical dynamics, microbial composition, and pathogenesis in the gut (6, 7). Studies illustrate that high-fat diets can break colonization resistance to enteric pathogens (8–11). Shifts towards high-fat diets and a rise in antibiotic resistance emphasizes the necessity for targeted therapeutics (12, 13). Understanding the metabolic relationships of pathogens, like *Salmonella*, over time and in different diet backgrounds is challenging but essential for designing interventions that minimize harm to the host and microbiome.

By pairing multi-omics technologies, we can better characterize these microbial interactions, yet robust genome-resolved resources in mouse models with representative diets across time are limited. To address this, we presented CBA_DREAMM (CBA Data Repository of Expression, Amplicon, Metagenomic, Metabolites) which incorporates 16S rRNA amplicon sequencing, metatranscriptomic sequencing, bacterial metagenome assembled genomes (MAGs), viral MAGs, as well as both targeted and untargeted metabolites across various time points, diets, and pathogen perturbations. This resource serves as a comprehensive tool for research in pathogenesis and in the CBA mouse model.

SECTION 2

Together, CBA_DREAMM contains 1754 16S rRNA amplicon samples, 17 deeply sequenced metagenomic samples (972 Gbp), 61 time-series metatranscriptomics samples (1521 Gbp), 2742 untargeted metabolomics samples, and 13 targeted short chain fatty acid samples, adding diet and time dimensionality (3, 5, 14–16). Fecal samples were collected from mice infected with *Salmonella* and pretreated with a high-fat diet, uninfected mice fed a high-fat diet, mice infected with *Salmonella* and fed a fibrous chow diet, uninfected mice fed a fibrous chow diet, and mice fed a fibrous chow diet and inoculated with dextran sodium sulfate as an inflammatory control. Specific methods for mouse experimentation with approval by the Ohio State University Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC; OSU 2009A0035), DNA and RNA

extraction, bacterial and viral genome generation, metatranscriptomic analysis, and targeted short chain fatty acid (SCFA) and untargeted metabolomics are detailed here (3, 5, 14–16).

Amplicon sequencing raw data for all samples was processed using Qiime2 2019.10 with specific steps described here (17). In short, raw data fastq files were demultiplexed in Qiime2. Then DADA2 was used for quality filtering, dereplication, denoising, removing chimeras and merging sequences. Amplicon sequence variant (ASV) taxonomy was determined via SILVA release 132 SSU Ref NR 99 (18) (see data accessibility). Our genome-resolved metagenome database was assembled using previously published methods (5, 15). Critical to this mission was the collection of deep metagenomic sequencing, with over 11 times more sequencing depth per sample (mean ~57 Gbp/sample) than the 5 Gbp commonly used in most gut metagenome studies (19–21).

Together, we provide i) 23,668 amplicon sequencing variants, ii) 970 MQHQ bacterial MAGs, iii) 2351 viral MAGs, of which 160 bacterial genomes and 609 viral genomes are unique when dereplicated(5), iv) ~25 Gbp/sample of metatranscriptomic data across time and in two distinct diet backgrounds, v) 1220 annotated metabolites through untargeted metabolomics, and vi) targeted metabolite concentrations of three important SCFAs. Novelty highlighted in this work includes identifying MAGs at early infection time points (e.g. day 1 after inoculation), phage genomic content (viral MAGs) which are known drivers of microbiomes, high-fat diet relevant MAGs, and the ability to detect metabolic nuance through our multi-omics approach. For example, in a fibrous chow diet background, *Salmonella*-induced inflammation reduced the abundance of dominant members like *Clostridia*, favoring the survival of *Lactobacillus* and *Enterococcus* (3, 5). Lastly, the amplicon and SCFA analyses highlighted the role in pathogen dosing and inflammation in microbiome restructuring (3). Ultimately, these tools become more powerful when combined, describing complex interaction across time, diet, and the pathobiome. These insights may lead to the development of rationally designed therapeutics in the context of an ever-changing microbial landscape. Multi-omics data tools, such as CBA_DREAMM, are crucial for advancing knowledge of these complex gut ecosystems and enabling researchers with limited computational resources access to valuable information.

Data availability statement: The sequence data supporting the results of this article are available in the National Center of Biotechnology Information (NCBI) under Bioproject number PRJNA348350. All sequencing outputs, taxonomy, and annotations are included on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10929037>)

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ASD, MS, and IL conducted mouse experiments and collected fecal and cecal samples. RAD performed DNA and RNA extractions, ensuring quality control. YK and VHW managed LC-MS/MS sample preparation and data collection for metabolomics. KK, RAD, YK, IL, MS, and JRR analyzed and interpreted sequencing and metabolomic data. ASD and BMMA provided expertise on *Salmonella* physiology and experimentation. MAB and KCW provided guidance on microbial metabolism and sequencing best practices. KK and KCW led the manuscript writing, with MAB and BMMA contributing edits. The authors declare no competing interests.

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